

GENERAL CONCEPTS UNDERSTANDING THE NUMBERING OF NEGATIVE INTEGER NUMBERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10693407>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 17th February 2024

Accepted: 19th February 2024

Published: 22th February 2024

KEYWORDS

numbering, numbers, decimals, hundreds, thousands, negative numbers, positive numbers, arithmetic course.

ABSTRACT

According to the program, introducing students to the naming of numbers begins in the 1st grade. They learn how to name numbers, compare them, find the fraction of a number, and find the number itself according to the given fraction. In the 4th grade, they will have an idea of the fraction of 1 and several fractions and its written form. In geometry, the concept of naming is directly connected with the proportion of sections, the proportion of middors and the proportions of other geometric shapes.

INTRODUCTION. In our country, the opportunities and attention given to young people are increasing, and at the same time, the methodology of teaching mathematics in primary classes is developing.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's confidence in the youth is evident from these words.

"We must not forget that the foundation of our future is created in the fields of knowledge, in other words, the future of our nation depends on the education and upbringing of our children today.

For this, every parent, teacher, and coach needs to see each child as a person first of all. Based on this simple requirement, we should accept that the main goal and task of education should be to raise our children to be perfect people who have the ability to think independently and broadly, and live consciously. This requires that education and training be carried out harmoniously.

METHODOLOGY

Numbering all non-negative numbers and performing arithmetic operations on them form the basis of the elementary mathematics course. Work on whole negative numbers is carried out during 4 years of study in primary school. The mathematics program provides for entering information about natural numbers and zeros in tens, hundreds, thousands, and multi-digit numbers. Each concentration, according to its content, reflects the main issues of the course of systematic arithmetic, so students learn to number numbers within certain limits and

operations on these numbers, and form an idea about the essence of arithmetic in general. . Dividing decimals allows you to study the main issues related to the features of the decimal numbering system and the oral and written numbering of numbers. Reading, writing, comparing numbers 1-10, composition of two numbers; the principle of formation of the natural series, the use of mathematical symbols, ($>$, $<$, k , k , $-$ signs) working with geometric shapes, zero (0) number and number, conscious and mechanical counting of things, counting in groups, creating didactic games, Grinding and forming 10 pennies week, act, then, centimeter, kg, liter.

DISCUSSION

“Ten”, room, unit of room, rules for writing 2-digit numbers in white and white, difference between a number and a number, methods of adding and subtracting numbers by connecting numbers, measuring and forming dismeter, meter, hour, minute, 20 tyen, 90 tyen, 1 som , comparison, x : signs, verbal and written numbering, abacus, drawing, making geometric shapes.

Within 1000 “Hundreds”, unit III, adding and writing 3-digit numbers, the principle of orin value of numbers, adding and subtracting 3-digit numbers by adding them, comparing, writing 3-digit numbers in the form of hundreds, tens, sums of units. Mm, km, day, month, year, second, century, time, diameter, segment, sector, dm cube, m cube, price, expressing them in other units, measuring geometric shapes, dividing into parts, comparison.

In high-digit numbers

The concept of “thousandth”, “class” is the logical composition of numbers, reading and writing 4-9 digit numbers, comparing, increasing and decreasing numbers by 10, 100, 1000 times. Onli number system, positional and non-positional number systems, strengthening the relationship between quantities, analysis of numbers.

Numbering and performing operations on non-negative whole numbers is one of the main topics in the elementary mathematics course. Elements of algebra and geometry are included in the system of arithmetic knowledge as much as possible, as a result of which the concepts of numbers, arithmetic operations and positives are reduced to a higher level.

Work on natural numbers and zero is carried out during the 4-year course in primary classes. The mathematics program is designed to gradually enter information about natural numbers and zero in concentrations of 10, 100, 1000, multi-digit numbers.

Dividing into points makes it possible to repeatedly look at the main issues related to the features of the digital numbering system, oral and written numbering.

Learning the first number involves counting things, learning the names, sequence, designation of numbers 1-10, different methods of comparing numbers (on the basis of performing operations on suitable sets of objects and the contents of numbers according to the position occupied in the series of compared numbers).

THE RESULT

Some important generalizations are formed in students in the early stages of education, for example, it is determined how each consecutive number in the natural series is formed, the relationship between the arbitrary number of the series and the numbers that come before and after it is established, etc.

When studying numbers in decimal, the number zero is also known. In this case, zero head is entered as a total characteristic. According to the current program, the second tenth is not allocated to a separate concentration. However, when learning to number within 100, the 2nd grade math textbook first considers numbering between 11-20 and then between 21-100. Studying the 2nd decimal in learning numbering helps to better understand the decimal composition of numbers and the principle of orin-value of numbers, forms new knowledge for students, that is, forms the concept of decimals as a unit of counting.

At the same time, verbal and written numbering of numbers and the mental composition of these numbers are organized. Based on the knowledge of the natural sequence of numbers and their decimal composition, cases of addition and subtraction in the form of 13-1, 17-1, 10-3, 16-6, 19-10 are considered.

When learning to number numbers within 1000 and multi-digit numbers, they get acquainted with the concepts of hundreds and thousands, the principle of formation of new counting units, and the concepts of classes are reduced.

CONCLUSION

Counting in 10's is the basis for mastering counting because other units count just like regular ones. The names and designations of first decimal numbers serve as a basis for derivation and designation of any other multi-digit number. Therefore, the primary task of the teacher is to determine the level of mathematical preparation of children entering the 1st grade. Such a check can be done at the time of admission of children to school, or during the initial training. The atmosphere for knowledge testing should be friendly.

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